

Original Article

Acute malnutrition and its determinants among children under five years of age using mid upper arm circumference (MUAC) in Lahore

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Study was conducted to assess the nutritional status of children below 5 years of age using mid upper arm circumference (MUAC) and its determinants. **Materials & Methods:** This analytical cross-sectional study was carried out in Akhtar Saeed Teaching Hospital Lahore and Lady Wallington Hospital Lahore from April 2019 till Oct 2019. Using systematic random sampling technique, 225 children were enrolled in the study. A self-structured questionnaire was used to record sociodemographic details and feeding practices. MUAC was measured by a non-stretch measuring tape. Malnutrition was categorized into severe acute malnutrition (MUAC; <115mm) and moderate acute malnutrition (MUAC; 115mm-124mm). Data were analysed using SPSS Version 22. Chi square test was applied. p-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant. **Results:** The mean age of children is 2.43 ± 0.75 years. Malnutrition was observed in 54.6% participants. Severe acute malnutrition (SAM) was found in 59 (26.2%) children and moderate acute malnutrition (MAM) was found in 64 (28.4%). Children at the risk of developing malnutrition were 32 (14.2%) while remaining 70 (31.1%) were well nourished. The percentage of severe malnutrition was more in female children. Delayed initiation of breast feeding (p value=0.008), poor economic status (p value=0.004), incomplete immunization status (p value=0.003), poor appetite (p value=0.001) and frequent episodes of illness (p value= <0.001) were significantly associated with malnutrition. **Conclusion:** Prevalence of malnutrition in children aged <5 years was high. Girl child was more vulnerable to become malnourished. Delayed initiation of breast feeding, poor economic status, incomplete immunization, poor appetite and frequent episodes of illness were significantly associated with malnutrition.

Keywords: Malnutrition, MUAC, under-five children

Introduction

Globally, malnutrition in children is a significant community health issue and is a major cause mortality and episodes of illness among children less than five years of age.¹ Malnutrition adversely affects cognitive and physical development of children. Malnourished children are vulnerable to irreversible long-term risks such as short stature, low immunity and increased susceptibility to infections.²

Under five children are considered the most vulnerable segment and their nutritional status and death rate is a sensitive indicator of the community's health and nutrition.³ Worldwide, according to an estimate, wasting, severe wasting and stunting was observed in 52 million, in 16 million and in 155 million children respectively.⁴ Malnutrition accounts for deaths of about 2 million children per year and is cause of 15 % of all disability-adjusted life years lost in children.⁵ According to a study conducted in India, 44.6% children below 5 years of age were stunted, 33.5% were wasted and 18.3% had SAM.⁶ Pakistan has unexpectedly higher prevalence of malnutrition and county ranked 77th among 113 countries.⁷ Pakistan's national survey reveal that malnutrition is still a major challenge. Among children below 5 years of age, prevalence of stunting is 40% and wasting is 18%. Nearly, 5 million children suffer from wasting, or low weight for height.⁸

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aimed to eliminate malnutrition by 2030. Target 2.2 of SDG 2 emphasizes to end all forms of malnutrition by 2030. It includes achievement of internationally agreed targets on stunting and wasting in children under 5 years of age by 2025.⁹ Pakistan is the signatory of this road map to achieve a better and more sustainable future.

Identification of acute malnutrition in children under 5 years of age is thus priority for timely treatment and ultimately to avoid child morbidity and mortality.¹⁰ Many anthropometric

measurements have been used to assess the nutritional status in children. However, measurement of middle of the Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) is considered as an easy, swift and valid method to detect malnutrition in this age group.¹¹ World Health Organization (WHO) endorse MUAC as an independent diagnostic criterion for severe acute malnutrition (SAM). The latest guidelines define severe acute malnutrition in 6months to five years of age children as: weight-for-height z-score <-3.0 and/or MUAC <115 mm and/or bilateral pitting oedema.¹²

It is very important to identify malnourished children at initial stages in order to provide them nutritional support as early as possible. The evidence generated through this study may bridge the knowledge gap and may help policy makers to develop effective strategies for reduction in magnitude of child malnutrition. The objective of this study was to assess the nutritional status of children below 5 years of age using mid upper arm circumference (MUAC) and its determinants.

Methodology

This hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted in Akhter Saeed Teaching Hospital Lahore and Lady Wallington Hospital Lahore after the approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB no M-18/027/-CM) from April 2019 till Oct 2019. Sample size was calculated to be 225 children six months to five years of age using Rao soft sample size calculator. Systematic random sampling technique was used. All children 6 months to five years of age visiting hospitals and their mothers willing to participate were included in study. Children with congenital anomalies and metabolic disorders were excluded. Research questionnaire was based upon questions used in previous studies. A self -structured pretested questionnaire was used to record sociodemographic details and feeding practices. MUAC was used as a quick diagnostic tool for detection of malnutrition. A non-stretch

tape measure was used for measurement of MUAC on left arm. Malnutrition was categorized into SAM (MUAC; <115mm) and moderate acute malnutrition i.e MAM (MUAC; 115mm-124mm). MUAC of between 125mm and 135mm was regarded as that child is at risk of acute malnutrition, while value above 135 was considered as child having appropriate nutritional status.

Data were entered and analysed using SPSS Version 22. Mean \pm standard deviation and frequency (percentage) were calculated. Chi square test was applied. p-value \leq 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results

The mean age of children is 2.43 ± 0.75 years. There was predominance of males 140 (62.2%) over females 85 (37.8%). Majority of the children 133(59 %) were more than two years of age. About one third of children, 72 (32%) were from extended families, while 153(68%) were from nuclear families. Out of 225, 194 study participants were residents of Lahore and 31(13.8%) were residing outside Lahore. About 86% or mothers were housewife and only 14% were working women.

Table-1: Socio-demographic variables

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age of child		
< one year	36	16
1-2 Years	56	24.8
More than 2 years	133	59.1
Gender		
Male	140	62.2
Female	85	37.7
Residence		
Within Lahore	194	86.2
Outside Lahore	31	13.7
Mother's occupation		
Housewife	193	85.7
Working women	32	14.2
Type of family		
Extended	72	32
Nuclear	153	68

Family Income per month		
Up to 15000/-	44	19.5
15000/- to 30000/-	136	60.4
More than 30000/-	45	20

Malnutrition was observed in 54.6% study participants. SAM (MUAC <115mm) was found in 59 (26.2%) children and MAM (MUAC 115mm-124mm) was found in 64 (28.4%). The no of children at the risk of developing malnutrition was 32 (14.2%) while remaining 70 (31.1%) were well nourished. The percentage of severe malnutrition was more in female children as 27% had MUAC less than 115 mm. Among 140 male children, 25.7% were severely malnourished. Percentage of moderate malnutrition were more in female children (29.4%) as compared to male children (27.8%). However, the association was insignificant. Highest prevalence of SAM was noted among age group 6months to one year. MAM was highest in age group more than 2 years. A higher percentage of children who were not exclusively breast fed in first 6 months of life had SAM and MAM, but this association was not significant. Significant association was observed in low monthly family income and under 5 years children malnutrition (p value=0.004). High prevalence of SAM and MAM was found in children of families having monthly income ranging from 15000 to 30000/-.

Fig 1. Assessment of Nutritional level using MUAC

Children who were not fully immunized showed higher prevalence (46.7%) of SAM. Significant association was found between appetite of child and malnutrition (p value=0.001) as 37% of children having poor appetite showed sign of SAM (MUAC less than 115 mm). Occurrence of frequent episodes of illness are significantly related to malnutrition in children. About 36.4% and 23.4% children who suffered from frequent episodes of illness had SAM and MAM respectively. Results are described in Table no 2.

Table-2: Relationship of sociodemographic variable with MUAC (n=225)

Variables	MUAC				p value
	Less than 11.5 cm	11.5 - 12.4 cm	12.5 - 13.5 cm	More than 13.5 cm	
Age of Child					0.63
< one year	9(25)	9(25)	5(13.9)	13(36.1)	

1-2 years	20(35.7)	15(26.8)	6(10.7)	15(26.8)	
>2 years	30(22.5)	40(30)	21(15.6)	42(31.6)	
Family Income					0.004
Up to 15000	11(25)	12(27.2)	10(22.7)	11(25)	
15000-30000	43(31.6)	43(31.6)	15(11)	35(25.7)	
More than 30000	5(11.1)	9(20)	7(15.5)	24(53.3)	
Interval between the subject child and the immediate elder child					.068
Only or first child	27(27.8)	30(30.9)	10(10.3)	30(30.9)	
Less than 2 years	14(31.8)	9(20.4)	12(27.3)	9(20.4)	
More than 2 years	18(21.4)	25(29.8)	10(11.9)	31(36.9)	
Breast feeding started within half an hour after birth					0.008
Yes	28(19.1)	43(29.4)	25(17.1)	50(34.2)	
No	31(39.2)	21(26.6)	7(8.8)	20(25.3)	
Exclusive breast feeding for 6 months					0.18
Given					
Not given	36(23)	42(26.9)	24(15.4)	54(34.6)	
	23(33.3)	22(31.9)	8(11.6)	16(23.1)	
Weaning started at 6 months					0.28
Yes	46(24.6)	56(29.9)	29(15.5)	56(29.9)	
No	13(34.2)	8(21)	3(7.9)	14(36.8)	
Child immunization					0.003
Fully immunized					
Not immunized	38(21.1)	53(29.4)	26(14.4)	63(35)	
	21(46.7)	11(24.4)	6(13.3)	7(15.5)	
Mother's perception on child's appetite					0.001

Feeding well	16(14.7)	40(36.7)	15(13.8)	38(34.8)	
Decreased appetite	43(37)	24(20.7)	17(14.6)	32(27.6)	
Frequent episodes of illness					<0.001
Reported	39(36.4)	25(23.4)	20(18.7)	23(21.5)	
Not reported	20(16.9)	39(33)	12(10.2)	47(39.8)	

Discussion

Malnutrition is the fundamental cause of morbidity and mortality among the children less than five years of age.^{13,14}

Findings of the study show that MUAC was less than 115mm in 26.2% children showing SAM, was between 115 to 124 in 28.4% children showing MAM. Only 31.1% had optimum nutritional status. Haq IU et al conducted a study in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The reported prevalence of MUAC-based malnutrition in their study was 46%.¹⁵ The higher prevalence in current study may be due to difference of geographical area.

The prevalence of severe malnutrition was more in female children as 27% had SAM and 29.4 % had MAM as compared to prevalence of SAM 25.7% and MAM 27.8% in male children. However, the association was insignificant. These findings are in accordance with the study conducted in Pakistan which showed malnutrition among female children was more prevalent (20.4%) as compared to male children (14.8%).¹⁶ In male oriented societies, male child gets larger share of more nutritious food, even if the resources of family are less.

This study reflected, that children between 1-2 years of age are mostly affected as 35.7% have SAM while 26.8% have MAM. Researchers who conducted a study in Nepal found that SAM was significantly higher among children of the age group 6–24 months. This finding may be attributed

to suboptimal feeding practices among this age group.¹⁷

This study reflects significant association between family income and child malnutrition. Higher percentage of SAM was seen in children whose monthly family income was low. Another study conducted in Southern India described that about two third of cases belonged to low socioeconomic group.¹⁸

Feeding practices have a significant impact on nutritional status of children. Initiation of breast feeding, exclusive breast feeding, and timely initiation of weaning also have significant effects on the child's nutritional status. In this study, higher percentage of children who did not receive breast feeding within half an hour after birth, were assessed to have SAM or MAM. Higher percentage of children who were not exclusively breast fed had SAM (33.3%) or MAM (31.9%). Another research conducted at China described that for children < 36 months lesser duration of breastfeeding and low percentage of exclusive breast feeding up to 6 months of age were major reason for malnutrition.¹⁹

In this study there was no significant association malnutrition with initiating time of weaning. However, nutritional status of children who were given weaning based upon combination of different food categories was better. Another study conducted in Sahiwal, Pakistan had different

findings, showing that malnutrition was more in children who received delayed weaning.²⁰

Appetite of child was directly related to nutritional status. SAM malnutrition was more common in children having poor appetite. Study conducted in Multan also showed that approximately two third malnourished children had poor appetite.²¹

Findings of this study revealed that severe malnutrition was more common in children who are not completely vaccinated. Similar results were described by researches in a study conducted in Tharparkar, Pakistan. Significant association between malnutrition and vaccination status was found in both studies.²²

There is a vicious circle of episodes of illness and development of malnutrition. The current study shows significant association between frequently reported episodes of illness and child's malnutrition. Hoq M *et al* in their study conducted in Bangladesh reported that episodes of illness were reported more in children with acute malnutrition in the last 2 weeks.²³

The results of this study would be helpful for policymakers for developing strategies for the prevention and treatment of malnutrition.

Conclusion

Malnutrition was observed in 54.6% study participants. Severe acute malnutrition (SAM) was found in 59 (26.2%) children and moderate acute malnutrition (MAM) was found in 64 (28.4%). Female children were more likely to become malnourished rather than males. Findings of research show that delayed initiation of breast feeding, having poor economic status, incomplete immunization status, decreased appetite and frequent episodes of illness were major risk factors that contributing to the child severe acute malnutrition.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Contributions of the Authors

SM did literature research, data collection, drafting and wrote the manuscript

IM conceptualized the project, did drafting and revision

